

Our Heritage, Our Stories

*Linking and searching Community-Generated Digital Content
to develop the people's national collection*

1.0 Details of the Community Fund Recipient

Name (s): Emma Semple, Ingrid Shearer, Nella McNicol, Abi L Glen

Organisation: The Pipe Factory (Strangeways), Glasgow Building Preservation Trust (GBPT)

Partner(s): OHOS

Amount received: 400.00

Please provide a brief description of the activities undertaken through the Community Fund:

With a small budget, teams of participants were challenged to find an object of note and bring it back to the Barras Hunt crew, comprised of volunteers from OHOS, the Pipe Factory, and Glasgow Building Preservation Trust. Working with the staff, the teams built their own stories around the objects, speculating on their connections to the local area, and took part in semi-structured interviews held by the OHOS team. The event showcased the crucial theme at the core of OHOS research:

“What are our stories, how do we share them, and how do stories become heritage? And how do we embed ephemeral stories into the concrete documentation and official narratives that describe and shape public awareness and understanding of heritage?”

The event built a guerilla community archive which explored hidden connections between objects found at the market and the iconic landmark of the Barras. 3D scans were then taken of several of the objects. The event upheld OHOS aims by exploring the novel ways that a digital community archive can be formed and preserved, and the often tactical and rapid approaches to archiving that may have to be developed, while also encouraging residents to consider their own attachments to local heritage.

2.0 Benefits to the Participants

Please write up to 800 words on how the activity benefited the participants. This could include anything from technical skills gained, to confidence in the worth of CGDC/ their own collections.

For example, did the activity produce new resources with strong community significance, or to extending/enhancing such existing content? Perhaps it developed innovative methods of managing content that will substantially benefit community groups (individually or more broadly), or to developing community skills in archival approaches.

This activity produced a substantial 'guerilla' archive of objects selected by participants, including everything from a wooden bear to old video game equipment. As far as we are aware, this is the first activity of this type to happen at the Barras, thus developing an innovative way of approaching the history and archiving of the landmark.

Participants engaging in the activity built skills in archival approaches; each participant was asked to reflect on their objects through a series of questions (see Appendix 1). These questions were designed to encourage teams to see themselves as archivists and consider any links between their objects and the local community.

Please see Appendix 2 for participant findings.

Summary of Findings

Participants and Purchases

- **Participants:** Approx. 40 attendees (25 sign-ups and ~15 walk-ins).
- **Items Purchased:** Wide variety of vintage and preloved items, including vases, teapots, hand mirrors, ceramics, knitted dresses, tapes, and a vintage Wii console.

Reoccurring Themes

1. **Materiality:** Strong emphasis on aesthetics, texture, and color in items chosen, reflecting personal and emotional connections to objects.

*"Besides being very beautiful and quite fun the first thing my father gave my mother was a bat's skull, so I have a special affinity with bats" - **A participant talking about their purchase, a Victorian lithograph of a long-eared bat.***

2. **Reuse and Sustainability:** Many participants appreciated items for their history, environmental significance, and the idea of giving them a "new chapter."

*“I noticed most people have bought ceramics, likely because they can be repurposed. All the items bought has a history, nobody bought something modern” – **Mary talking about her purchase, a silver brooch***

3. **Heritage and Local Culture:** Discussions highlighted connections to local industrial and cultural histories, storytelling, and the significance of traditional crafts.

*“I appreciate industrial histories and have a love for tools and industry” - **Nathalie and Lulu talking about their purchases, sharpened tools for carving***

4. **Emotional and Practical Value:**
 - a. Items sparked memories, represented loved ones, or provided a sense of connection to the past.
 - b. Functional value noted in some items like tea sets and furniture.

*“Something about knowing so many hands have held them and people have looked at them over the years really warms my heart!” - **Nathalie and Lulu***

5. **Archival Qualities:** Participants expressed diverse perspectives on archival work:
 - a. Traits such as organization, curiosity, patience, and empathy were mentioned.
 - b. Archives are seen as both a way to preserve and democratize access to history.

*“To be an archivist you need curiosity, creativity, interest in preserving memories and understanding” - **Ruth and Eva***

Notable Individual Reflections

- Several participants linked purchases to personal memories or aspirations (e.g., a chicken bag symbolizing a future goal of owning chickens).
- Items often prompted reflections on life, storytelling, and history (e.g., stained glass, vintage brooches, and ceramics).
- Items were seen as carriers of social histories, often linked to family or community narratives.

Relation to Broader Themes

- **Community Representation:** Stories of everyday lives and local histories are valued, especially women's roles and less-documented narratives.

- **Post-Custodialism:** Participants emphasized the importance of making archives accessible and relevant, underscoring the idea that “anyone can be an archivist.”

Key Takeaways

- Vintage and preloved items serve as bridges to history, offering tangible links to culture, identity, and heritage.
- Emotional and practical motivations guide purchasing decisions, rooted in memory, functionality, and connection.
- Community-focused archival practices resonate with participants, highlighting the importance of inclusivity in preserving and sharing history.

Case Study: Linda, Barry the Barras Bear, and The Barras Market as a Living Archive

The first team to join the Barras Hunt was Linda and her son Gary. They purchased Barry the Barras Bear, a homemade wooden bear smoking a cigarette.

Gary explained that he thought the bear was appropriate as it was quirky, befitting the reputation that you can buy anything from the Barras, and that its cigarette linked it back to the Pipe Factory’s original use. This led to a discussion of the market’s changing reputation

and clientele as times have shifted, like how the once thriving pipe industry building has become the site of a modern social enterprise.

The Market as an Archive of Migration and Perception:

Linda sees the Barras as a place where the history of migration and social transformation is tangible. Through its stalls and artifacts, the market reflects the community's past perceptions and prejudices, providing a stark reminder of social change. For example, Linda notes that today, she has seen still of Al Jolson performing in blackface, and blackface adverts for Pears soap, which were once commonplace but are now widely recognized as inappropriate. Such items serve as a testament to the shifting societal norms and the power of archives to document these changes.

Connections and Community

Linda continued by noting that for her and a lot of her community, the Barras is more than a market—it's a space of laughter, connection, and continuity. The market's infamous banter has remained a constant, a source of humour and warmth that her children fondly remember: "They used to say, 'Can we go to the Barras? The Barras is funny!'", referring to the chat of the stall holders with their customers. However, she wonders whether today's children perceive the Barras with the same curiosity and joy. As gentrification begins to reshape the area, and younger artists populate the market, the old stalls and their wares remain, raising questions about whether the market is becoming a parody of its former self or retaining its authenticity.

Family Archives and Emotional Labour:

Linda's passion for preserving family history has led her to maintain a personal archive, collecting stories and artifacts that anchor her to the past. She views this emotional labour as a way of coping with change and fostering connections with her family, while keeping her bound to the history of the East End.

The Market's Role in Identity and Inclusion:

Linda believes the Barras embodies a "bottom-up" approach to archiving, where anyone can contribute to the preservation of history. In a world often shaped by gatekeepers and top-down decision-making, the Barras can stand as a grassroots archive, showcasing the everyday lives, struggles, and triumphs of the East End community. It also serves as a reminder, as Linda says, that "anyone can be an archivist".

3.0 Benefits to OHOS

Please write up to 800 words on how the activity met with OHOS aims and objectives.

You should consider the ways in which the activity expanded the diversity of materials, peoples, and stories represented within the UK national collection and showcases the diversity and complexity of our cultural heritage.

You may reflect in how far the activity/outputs:

....foreground historically under-represented communities and histories.

.... challenges existing narratives or practices.

....Served to connect diverse sets of people and stories.

....enabled people taking part to learn more about CGDC.

... encouraged people taking part to learn about OHOS and how it can support their archive's goals

... enabled people taking part to have new experiences by exploring their collections

... encouraged people taking part to share experience, skills and information about their archives/collections

The value of the event for OHOS was that it showcased the direct connections between stories and object, and explored how those stories may become part of an archive. The event enabled a broad and inclusive dialogue about how stories are embedded into objects, and the challenges around then embedding those stories into the documentation of the objects that may become part of an archive. The transient nature of the workshop attendees, present only for a very brief time, during which their stories, memories, and experiences were captured, reflected the layered ways that community archives develop, and how the relationships between archival practice and community expertise can be sustained in liminal and porous ways.

4.0 Reflections

The novelty of the activity encouraged each participant to see themselves as community archivists (if just for one day), and certainly allowed them to have new experiences. It connected a diverse set of people and stories; participants came from all over the city of Glasgow, but also China, Malaysia, the south of England, Canada, and the USA. In this way, the activity showcased the diversity of people interested in UK community heritage, and the draw of the Barras. It has also recategorised the market as a site of rich archival material.

Several of the participants came from heritage backgrounds and were thus able to share skills and information about the objects or about archiving processes within their own organisations. Because OHOS team members were conducting informal “interviews” with the teams and their objects, they were able to weave in discussions around CGDC and the aims of OHOS.

The Barras Hunt highlighted the strong links the OHOS project has found between heritage and the stories told and shared. Ultimately, heritage is shaped by stories; heritage is about stories and these stories represent a variety of social and cultural backgrounds.

The Barras Hunt allowed the OHOS team to further solidify the important links between the stories shared and the language, terms and expressions used to describe these stories. Consequently, ensuring this rich data in stories is communicated and retained in the documentation of the digital content maintained by archives is a vitally important part of the information lifecycle. The Barras Hunt has identified ways that stories can be captured in documentation and metadata, and in turn how this is expressed in the post custodial model of working with community heritage.

Appendix 1

Questions for Participants

Introductory Questions

- Would you consider yourself an archivist (are you an archivist)? What skills do you need to be an archivist? Do you think anyone can be an archivist?
- What is an archive? What do you think makes up an archive? Will these materials come from the community or somewhere else? Who is the archive for? Who do you think is represented in the archive?

Material Questions

- We asked you to find us an item in the Barras that you think tells a story – why did you choose this item? What story does it tell? What does it tell us about the local area? What does it tell us about the local community?
- Do you notice a theme in the items on the table? Are the items categorisable? Do you see a connection between your chosen item and the items on the table?
- If you were in charge of exhibiting the items on the table to showcase the Barras and its community how would you arrange them?
- What is the historic significance of the materials?

Community Questions

- We have highlighted some of the connections between the items on the table and your chosen item. We also got you to reveal your own thoughts about the item and why it might be significant to you. Why is it important that this information is captured? What does it reveal about the area that might not be preserved in a mainstream institution/archive?
- How do you think preserving this information will affect the narrative about the local area/the Barras established by established institutions/archives? Will it be more

representative of the community? (this is an extremely leading question so will definitely need rewording!)

Appendix 2

Participant Input, Feedback and Thoughts

N/A	Natalie and Lulu:	Nathan & Deborah	N/A	Dan	Lachlan (wishes to remain anonymous) + mum
<p>Vase: Very pretty posy vase, loved the colours Would look very nice on bookcase</p>	<p>Hand mirror: old object in the hand getting a practical and new life</p> <p>Sharpened tools for carving: texture memory and woody colours Shelheld smithing & shipping industry??</p> <p>Ports/connection/ industrial histories & love of tools and industry</p> <p>Yes I think I'm an archivist its how I think and how I express love Knowing someone; intimacy of a body of worn</p>	<p>Lemon Sherbet: Like the taste, sweetie shop with the tubs = nostalgia interested in history, less packaging and plastic</p>	<p>Fox doorstep: Not what we were looking for, got character, seemed loved</p>	<p>Chicken bag, teapot, Scott Walker CD & NHS Badge:</p> <p>Chicken bag: Me and my girlfriend want to get pet chickens but we don't have the space! This bag will do for the time being!</p> <p>Teapot: I lost my teapot when I last moved flat, so I need a new one!</p> <p>NHS Badge: Because it</p>	<p>Wii Console and Games: We chose this because Lachlan loves vintage games and games consoles The box came from a flat clearance and the stall holder let us have the whole thing and the box! Its a collection that would have been all together and used by someone</p>

	<p>Intimacy and silence way of knowing someone</p> <p>Skills: patience, obsessiveness, though depends...empathetic</p> <p>Mainstream? Humanity isn't always represented – small lives lived</p> <p>It's an interesting time to do this work – how folks are responding to new stalls – like/dislike/ inform a more balanced way forward. Tangible history and heritage.</p> <p>I bought vintage hand mirror and vintage butter knives. I love hand mirrors and collect them; something about knowing so many hands have held them and people have looked at them over the years really warms my heart! Just under budget, thanks!</p>			<p>celebrates 50 years of the NHS in Scotland.</p> <p>Some of my friends have needed NHS care in recent years an I think its worth celebrating and fighting against its privatisation</p> <p>Scott Walker Album: Because I love this album and I have never seen it on sale anywhere before!</p>	
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N/A	Viktoria and Donald	N/A	Linda & Gary	N/A	N/A
<p>Knitted dress: homemade, 60s?? Vibe – ballroom! Cosy for Glasow winter</p>	<p>Chair: Beautiful, on budget, mint colour</p> <p>Archivist needs organisation, attention to details, little bit of knowledge Not anyone can be as need focus, An archive provides historical reference points = everything and anything, if its documents it should be in an archive Materials come from both local and global, archive is for everyone Fundamental to get something from it, Liked it because made them think of the many bums that sat on it, the children that would have likely played with it but still in good nick, looks happy The woman was moving out and something that she left behind</p>	<p>Tea pot: Loved the elegant shape and the design motifs, under budget! Reminds me of a 1950s Glasgow living room</p>	<p>Lost Gardens and Barry the Barras Bear: Link to East End (GU Campus), illustrations, smoking chat! + pipe factory, the humour of the displays at Barras “Art or a fire extinguisher?” Really could have been lost, History of Migration! 287 Gatekeepin g power and decision, bottom up/grassroots “we can’t have nice things” & perception of the East End.</p>	<p>China Tea set: Workmanshi p, hand crafted, afternoon tea as British tradition and chinese! Will all be used again!</p>	<p>Long eared bat (victorian ligraph): Besides being very beautiful and quite fun the first thing my father gave my mother was a bat’s skull, so I have a special affinity with bats Also I was a teen goth, obvs. Bats as family origin story History of craft and artistry which can be forgotten and hidden in tat & Pipe Factory Themes: “diff but really fucking cool”</p>

		<p>Archive is ways of perceptions , you can see what's inappropriate now and how far we've come (Al Jolson & Pears)</p> <p>Don't want to ever lose the Barras, everyone wants to be here when they (?)</p> <p>The banter never changes!</p> <p>Always funny</p> <p>"can we go to the Barras, it's funny!"</p> <p>Do kids have same perception?</p> <p>Still finding questionable items...</p> <p>Gentrification – Ralph Lorne1 Is it a parody of itself?</p> <p>Linda keeps a family archive – an interest in finding about</p>		<p>"A breathing exercise"</p> <p>Arrange: A sane market stall! Will record conversations</p> <p>Archive: Unintentional archivist – you need to be a keeper. Open to all!</p> <p>Good: Care</p> <p>Bad: Lack of common sense</p>
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			<p>history and stories, the emotional labour of the families</p> <p>Curiosity -> thirst for knowledge -> web of info - >learning things together</p> <p>Anchors to things past to cope with change and connect to family</p> <p>What's a historical archive & what's "stuff"</p> <p>Linda wishing she had done more history</p> <p>ANYONE can be an archivist</p>		
Gerry	Ruth & Eva	Rebecca and Kames	Mary	Rebecca and James (Tape – Para handy?)	Sophie, Erin, Millie
Stained glass decoration: Looks great on my window with my	Candle holder: Liked the colour and quality, unusual and useful, preloved Not drawn to vintage	Tape – Para handy: Scottish storytelling, Cally Uni, pub in	Brooch: Exotic, birds, old style victorian, water plant bird, I like	Storytelling – prompted off conversation and shared histories Serials in the papers;	Represented: WOMEN, we need to hear more about there households,

<p>victorian colour glass bottles. Great wee find at the Barras.</p>	<p>To be an archivist need curiosity, creativity, interest in preserving memories and understanding</p>	<p>Govan! (Rebecca and James?)</p>	<p>the vintage/olde r jewellery, is it old? Similar to others that I own, like the look, studied archaeology and material culture. To be an archivist needs to be: organised, clear handwriting ! And have some natural tendency towards the career Thinks of paper based records not objects when thinks of archive Archive = "made up of things" Archive should be for everybody but don't realise what they can access =</p>	<p>Govan pub; public seeing the boats; what life was like & necessity boat History focus on events rather than people – oral history teaches us more Preserve media in outdated forms (tapes – serials – oral hist) 1988 More accessible in different formats Interpretation of some material Yes to archivist (R) - J; physical media collections and fair use laws/entertainment Who for? Older folks: shared histories/memories to be passed on, social histories;</p>	<p>shopping and lives Important ? Stories get lost and we only realise when it's too late, it's such an integral part of Glasgow Multiple generations of stories Mainstream: Diff way of thinking about what's interesting, valuable, fun. An authentic snapshot its humanity putting the human back</p>
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			<p>opportunity to visit</p> <p>People who are more privileged.</p> <p>Original or style of?</p> <p>From somewhere exotic, think of travel, holiday, heirloom, not the most fashionable = makes you think of someone older, someone's granny, gendered</p> <p>Noticed most people bought ceramics, repurposing, all has history nobody bought modern, noticed a travel connection with other items</p>	<p>where newer traditions come from</p> <p>Gaelic original – stories lost to language, vital spark as lit and met connection</p> <p>Shift in narrative – making aluring vs mix more trends and old guard</p> <p>Same stories, same jokes</p> <p>Not being well documented in digital age</p>	
Steve	Vanessa				
Teapot(?) : Not an archivist,	Hong Kong Snacks stickers				

<p>more a “hoarder”, don’t feel he has the organ, archive are a collection of anything, sense of changes, objects that can be theoreticall y grouped together Archives need (?) and narrative , whats its significance Used to buy dodgy software (little folder in a catalogue) Theme? Quite a lot of ceramics Seale and ‘carryability’ was a feature, could digitally curate</p>	<p>(£3): From cream comes true stall Founded by people of HK heritage I rarely eat these nowadays – high carb, good to have stickers to remind myself of fond from Hond Kong – support my community too</p> <p>Delf small vase (£1) From a stall initially I was browsing a German plate -> tried to read the antiquarian script – felt bad for just browing but not buying so I got it. Also love blue and white Delft also embodies some Europe-China connection – interesting to reflect</p> <p>Meito China tea set (£6): Last purchase from the Cartwheel – founded by Noritake former employee I need a</p>				
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	<p>small cup and saucer!</p> <p>Doesn't consider herself an archivist, don't have the qualification</p> <p>Archivists need to know how to take care, common sense around preservation and conservation</p> <p>Archive should be findable and searchable and accessible as possible</p> <p>Archive for everyone</p> <p>Consider collection policy and is democratic</p> <p>"connection = giving away item a new chapter of life" how will the continue to interact, how function changes over time adds layers to the item</p> <p>Purpose and reason to buy items, original aim might shift, value can be measurable</p>				
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Reoccurring Themes:

Materiality: aesthetics, texture, colour, etc.

Reuse: Environmental reasons or previously loved and now new chapter

Link to heritage: Industrial, local, cultural, etc.

Connections

Value in its various forms: need, want, celebration, financial, quality

Archivist's qualities

Related to OHOS themes: community representation, post-custodialism